

Guidelines and Style for IRRI Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

New upland rice varieties for Senegal

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DJ.11.509 and IRAT133 are upland rices that have been tested for 4 yr by the National Rice Improvement Program in collaboration with the West Africa Rice Development Association at the ISRA Sefa Station. Results of direct-seeded varietal trials comparing the two rices with local 144 B/9 are in the table.

The new upland varieties have short duration (90–100 d) and are adapted to the local short rainy season (see table). They require specific crop management

because their vegetative period is short and tillering time is very limited. The new varieties performed well except in 1980 and 1982 when the local variety outyielded them.

The varieties were selected from TUNSART/TN1/H4 crossed in Senegal, and IRAT10 crossed at the Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales, Bouaké, Ivory Coast. DJ.11.509 is a semidwarf photoperiod-insensitive line and has highly synchronized flowering. It has longer grains than IRAT10. IRAT133 has intermediate plant height and photoperiod insensitivity. It has excellent early seedling vigor and intermediate tillering capacity. *ℒ*

Results of variety test of IRAT133 and DJ.11.509 in Senegal.^a

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1979 (911.9 mm)	1980 (699.3 mm)	1981 (1021.6 mm)	1982 (794.4 mm)
IRAT133	3.0	2.0	3.8	2.8
DJ.11.509	4.8	2.9	2.9	2.2
144 B/9	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.4

^a Values in parentheses indicate rainfall.

Land races of aromatic rice discovered in Taiwan

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Until recently, aromatic rice was not extensively grown in Taiwan, although rice has been grown there for thousands of years. Breeding for scented rice began at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station in 1977. Several promising aromatic strains, both sinica (keng) and indicas, were developed. Among them, Chianung-yu 269 (source of aroma: Taishosen from Japan), a sinica type, and Chianung-sen-yu 43 (source of aroma: IR841 from IRRI), an indica, are

expected to be named as varieties in 1985.

In 1983, we discovered at Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station that traditional aromatic rices were widely grown, though on limited hectareage, in many parts of the district. Farmers who planted the aromatic rice belong to the Ai-mei aboriginal tribe, one of several tribes in Taiwan. Other tribes do not plant aromatic rices.

The aromatic rices grown by Ai-mei farmers are tall and leafy with large panicles and long-awned grains. Yields are low (see table). Although the exact number of land races in the area has not been determined, there are large intra- and inter-varietal differences; therefore

Major agronomic characters of traditional and improved aromatic rices in Taiwan.^a

Variety or selection	Days to heading	Plant ht (m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield components			Panicles		Awn	Grain size			Pericarp color	Lodging
				Panicles per plant	Grains per panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Length (m)	Weight (g)		Length (cm)	Width (cm)	L/W		
Katupa-ai (Native) ^b	56	151	3.0	4.6	143	29.0	24.6	3.7	Long	0.78	0.37	2.11	Red	Severe
Chianung-yu 269 (japonica) ^c	64	100	5.3	11.3	131	24.2	18.3	3.1	None	0.69	0.33	2.09	White	Light
Chianung-se-yu 43 (indica) ^c	66	103	5.8	8.9	136	25.3	23.3	3.5	None	0.85	0.26	3.27	White	None

^aData collected in the second crop, 1984, at Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station experimental farm at Chi-an, Hualien. ^bGlutinous. ^cImproved selection.

these rices offer vast genetic diversity for breeding programs. Unfortunately, the area planted to aromatic rices is decreasing because of low yields and the difficulty in processing caused by long

awns. Steps must be taken to save this valuable germplasm.

The traditional aromatic rices grown in Hualien probably are land races indigenous to Taiwan, although their

existence and production have not been documented. Their origin is unclear, but it is likely that early Ai-mei settlers brought the seeds with them when they migrated to Taiwan. ☞

Performance of three elite rice mutants

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BINA instituted a mutation breeding program in 1973 with local Nizersail to develop early-maturing semidwarfs with high yield potential. In the M₂, several mutants were isolated from the gamma irradiated progenies. Subsequent generations were evaluated and Mut NS1, Mut NS2, and Mut NS5 were selected in 1981. They were evaluated for various agronomic characters at three Bangladesh sites and compared

Characteristics of mutants derived from Nizersail, Mymensingh, Bangladesh.^a

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Crop duration (cm)	Effective tillers/plant	Grains/panicle (g)	1000-grain wt	Grain yield (t/ha)
Mut NS1	148 a	145	10	184	18.2	5.2 d
Mut NS2	131 c	136	13	134	19.3	4.2 c
Mut NS5	91 e	136	12	110	20.1	5.3 ab
Nizersail	145 ab	155	13	118	18.5	4.3
BR4	115 d	148	10	153	21.7	5.5 a

^a Separation of means in a column at 5% level.

with Nizersail and BR4.

Varieties were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Plant height, crop duration, effective tillers per plant, grains per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and yield were recorded (see table),

Mut NS1 and Mut NS2 were tall add Mut NS5 was semidwarf. All three matured earlier than Nizersail and BR4. Mut NS1 and Mut NS5 yielded significantly higher than Nizersail, but similar to BR4. Both seem promising for a rice - wheat sequence. ☞

Intensity and duration of dormancy in some rices

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Seed dormancy in rice is a desirable trait, particularly in prekharif and kharif (wet) seasons, for preventing losses to preharvest sprouting of seeds. If intensity and duration of dormancy are high, farmers who intend to use the seed for the succeeding rice crop have problems.

We studied intensity and duration of dormancy of seeds of 12 photoperiod-sensitive tall indica rices collected from

Intensity and duration of dormancy of 12 photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivars, Chinsurah, India.

Group	Cultivar	Germination (%)		Dormancy	
		Control (30°C)	Treated (50°C)	Intensity ^a	Duration (wk)
Weak, short-duration dormancy	NC1281	19	94	Weak (2)	8
	Seetasail	30	97	Weak (2)	9
	OC1393	7	96	Weak (3)	10
Weak, long-duration dormancy	NC324	5	85	Weak (4)	16
	Badsabhog	10	83	Weak (4)	16
	Rupsail	23	88	Weak (3)	16
	Kalma 222	6	80	Weak (4)	15
Moderate, long-duration dormancy	Randhunipagal	1	78	Moderate (6)	16
	Kataribhog	13	77	Moderate (5)	16
	NC678	5	77	Moderate (5)	18
	Kumargore	2	76	Moderate (10)	14
	Patnai 23	12	73	Moderate (5)	18

^a Figures in parentheses indicate number of days required to attain 80% germination following 50°C heat treatment.